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Abstract: Polarization change curves, defined as a difference between the polarization curve at the beginning of life and the actual polarization curve after the cell has been operational for some time, were used to analyze degradation of a PEM fuel cell stacks. Such an analysis identified and quantified different losses due to degradation, i.e., it assessed the fuel cell state of health. In order to verify that this state of health assessment method indeed identifies the real causes of fuel cell degradation, it was applied to a controlled experiment involving a single cell with known or previously independently determined degradation mechanism(s) by being exposed to an accelerated stress test for electrocatalyst degradation. Degradation, i.e., loss of voltage was due to increase of activation losses and increase of resistance in the catalyst layer, both most likely due to the loss of catalyst electrochemically active area. The results of the polarization change curves analysis correspond to the findings of the periodic individual tests performed during the accelerated stress test, such as electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, cyclic voltammetry and linear sweep voltammetry. Therefore, this method has potential to be used as a relatively quick and simple, yet effective, state of health assessment tool.

Keywords : polarization-change curve, fuel cells, degradation, diagnostics, state of health

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Tests and performances evaluation of SoH approaches

1. Introduction

This task aimed at developing technique(s) and algorithm(s) that enable to continuously track the state of health (SoH) of the fuel cell stack. The selected method must be able to extract or build relevant features from raw data and to maximize the information content of features. Developed algorithms should be able to deal with imprecise, uncertain and incomplete data. Indeed, these tools must have the ability to “discover” new states of health and to integrate the transition between states. As the fuel cell performance (i.e., health) is best determined by its polarization curve, the polarization change curves were previously identified as a possibly viable method for characterization of fuel cell degradation, and consequently for assessment of its state of health.

2. Polarization Change Curves

Polarization change curves, which are defined as a difference between polarization curve at the beginning of life (BOL) and the actual polarization curve after the cell has been operational for some time, were used to analyze degradation of two PEM fuel cell stacks and a single cell exposed to different load cycles.

As explained in our previous report [1], there are four major sources of performance losses in PEM fuel cells, namely: 1) activation polarization, 2) ohmic losses, 3) concentration polarization, and 4) internal currents and/or crossover losses. Since an increase in magnitude for each of these phenomena (i.e. degradation) exhibits characteristic influence on the cell's polarization curve [2], by simply plotting the polarization change curves over time, one should be able to determine contributions of different sources of voltage losses (or polarizations) on the cell's performance. Limiting cases of all four polarization change curves are shown in Figure 1. An increase in activation (kinetic) losses should ideally result in a horizontal line, thus independent of current density. An increase in ohmic losses should show as an inclined straight line that intercepts the origin of the plot. An increase in transport losses (concentration polarization) should result in a curve exponentially rising with current density. And finally, an increase in internal currents and hydrogen crossover should have its maximum contribution at open circuit, while its influence should diminish rapidly with increase in current density. The overall polarization change curve is almost always a combination of the four limiting cases to some extent, as it is unrealistic to expect that only one type of polarization would increase with time, while others remain the same. The calculated curves shown in Figure 1 are not expected to be quantitatively accurate; instead, they should be used as simple qualitative indicators of the general shapes that result from different types of polarization degradation.

Figure 1 Contribution of different losses on the polarization change curve [2].

3. Application of Polarization Change Curves for Assessment of Degradation in PEM Fuel Cell Stacks

This relatively simple approach of performance degradation assessment was first applied on two PEM fuel cell stacks subjected to degradation tests.

The analyzed stacks were taken from a project's partner (ZSW) research on PEM fuel cell durability reported in Scholta et al. [3]. In their research they were examining durability of PEM fuel cell stacks fed with simulated reformat fuel, for different flow field designs and flow directions, different stack operating temperatures, and different relative humidities of the inlet gases. In total six stacks were subjected to long term degradation test under current control using a predefined 24 h load cycle, Figure 2.

Figure 2 Load cycle [3].

Every week, a polarization curve and OCV tests were performed and recorded. Both stacks chosen for the analysis here (stacks no. 4 & 5 from the paper [3]) consisted of 10 cells with the active area of 142 cm^2 and were operated in a co-flow configuration. The first stack was operated at $75 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (coolant inlet temperature), with dew points of $72 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (RH 88%) and $52 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (RH 35%) for the anode and cathode streams, respectively. The simulated reformat fuel consisted of hydrogen with 30 mol% CO_2 and 5 mol% CH_4 , with the addition of 10 ppm of CO. The stack was operated for about 1600 hours and exhibited an average degradation of $35.8 \text{ } \mu\text{Vh}^{-1}$ at 0.4 A cm^{-2} . The evolution of polarization curves for the average cell in the stack is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Polarization curves of the first analyzed stack (stack no. 4 in the paper) [3].

The resulting polarization change curves for individual cells in the stack, i.e., voltage loss between beginning of life (101 hours) and the end of the run (1605 hours), are shown in Figure 4. As it can be seen from the figure, distribution of voltage varies somewhat from cell to cell, with especially cell #1 (Series 10 here) exhibiting $\sim 10 \text{ mV}$ higher degradation than the rest of the stack. However, some general patterns still exist and some conclusion based on the polarization change curves can be drawn.

Figure 4 Polarization change curves for individual cells of the first analyzed stack: voltage loss between beginning of life (101 hours) and the end of the run (1605 hours) [4].

If a generally linear increase of the voltage loss in the range of 0.2 – 0.4 A cm⁻² is simulated with a straight inclined line, representing an increase in resistive (ohmic) losses, the intersection of this line with the vertical axis at 0 A cm⁻², should represent the activation losses (horizontal dashed line). According to the constructed polarization change curves, this particular stack exhibited increased activation losses of ~50 mV (or 33 μVh⁻¹), probably due to the loss of the electrochemical surface active area (ECSA). For the theoretical Tafel slope of ~70 mV dec⁻¹ at 75 °C, this should correspond to a decrease in ECSA of ~80%. The slope of the inclined line suggests increase in the cell resistance of ~60 mΩ cm² (or 0.04 mΩ cm² h⁻¹), while there seems to be only small contribution of mass transport losses (deviation from a straight line). It should be noted here that the increase in the ohmic resistance in a large part most likely originates from the degradation of cathode catalyst layer (CL), due to increased ionic resistance within the CL which cannot be measured directly. And finally, some cells show somewhat higher voltage differences at open circuit, indicating a possible increase in hydrogen crossover rate or in short circuit current.

The second analyzed stack was operated at a lower operating temperature of 65 °C (coolant inlet temperature), with dew points of 60 °C (RH 80%) for both streams. The cells in this stack also had a different type of MEA in comparison with the previously analyzed stack. These changes resulted in a much better durability and the stack exhibited average degradation of only 10.3 μVh⁻¹ at 0.46 A cm⁻² after 15 000 hours. The stack also operated with 0.8 vol% anodic air bleed that started only after 2700 hours. Polarization curve evolution of the average cell during the degradation for the second analyzed stack is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Polarization curves of the second analyzed stack (stack no. 5 in the paper) [3].

Since the stack operated at somewhat different operating conditions during the first 2700 hours, and an erratic behavior of voltage readings after 7900 hours, the polarization change curves shown in Figure 6 are calculated for the period of 2900 to 7900 hours. It is noticeable that the second stack exhibited practically no increase in activation losses or in hydrogen crossover/short circuit current for the analyzed 5000 hours. The resistive losses increased by $\sim 100 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ (or $0.02 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ h}^{-1}$, half the rate of the first stack), and some of the cells show noticeable increase in mass transport losses.

Figure 6 Polarization change curves for some of the cells in the second analyzed stack: voltage loss between 2900 and 7900 hours [4].

4. Verification of Polarization Change Curves for Assessment of Degradation in PEM Fuel Cells

In order to be sure that the selected state of health assessment method indeed identifies the causes of fuel cell degradation, it was applied to a controlled experiment involving a single cell with known or previously independently determined degradation mechanism(s).

A single cell analyzed here was subjected to an accelerated stress test (AST) at our own laboratory at FESB. The cell was a 50 cm² active area MEA manufactured by BASF (12E-W MEA) with a Nafion[®] 112 membrane, while the cell hardware was produced by FuelCellTechnologies, Inc. The flow fields were quadruple serpentine on the cathode and a single serpentine on the anode in a co-flow configuration.

The aim of the experiment was to degrade Pt catalyst, so the cell was exposed to a 49 seconds long potential cycling profile (Figure 7), modeled on the recommendations from the Department Of Energy AST protocol for electrocatalyst degradation. A more detailed description of the protocol and the experiment is reported in [1].

Figure 7 Accelerated Stress Test – Potential cycling profile [1].

Since the chosen operating conditions and the load profile were purposely very harsh, the whole experiment took only 5000 cycles (or ~68 hours) before it was stopped, as the cell degraded very rapidly. Polarization curves recorded during the experiment (T= 65°C; RHs 83.4%) are shown in Figure 1. It is significant that most of degradation occurs in the first 1000 cycles.

Figure 8 Evolution of polarization curves for the tested single cell [1].

During the experiments cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements were regularly conducted and relative sizes of ECSA, calculated from the CV recordings, are presented in Table 1. Along with the CV, linear sweep voltammetry measurements were also conducted and have shown that the crossover/short circuit current was practically constant throughout the experiment with $\sim 2 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$.

Table 1 Calculated ECSA from the cyclic voltammetry recordings.

	ECSA (%)
BOL	100
1000 cycles	47,1
3000 cycles	28,8
5000 cycles	22,4

The differences between voltage at the BOL and voltage after certain number of cycles are shown in Figure 9. As it can be seen from the figure, polarization change curves are practically straight lines and are simulated with linear functions with regression analysis showing $R^2 > 0,997$ in all cases.

Figure 9 Evolution of polarization change curves during the experiment for the tested single cell.

Activation losses of 31.1, 32.2 and 37.2 mV, calculated from the y-axis intercepts, for the theoretical Tafel slope ($\sim 67\text{mV dec}^{-1}$, at 65 °C) correspond to 65, 67 and 71% loss of the ECSA. Even though the values of ECSA obtained this way differ slightly from the ones obtained by CV measurements, the qualitative trends are very similar. The comparison of the ECSA values obtained with both approaches is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Comparison of differently obtained ECSA values.

The shape of the polarization change curves indicates that the most significant contribution to performance degradation is due to increase in an "ohmic-like" resistance. Both current interrupt and high frequency measurements showed an increase in the ohmic resistance from the initial $\sim 100 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ to the final $\sim 130 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$, which was achieved already after the first 1000 cycles. But this increase in measured ohmic resistance is not nearly enough to account for all the linear losses. However, both of these techniques can only measure ionic resistance in the membrane and all the electronic resistance through the cell hardware (including the contact resistance), but not the ionic resistance in the catalyst layer. One could assume that due to the linear shape of the polarization change curves, this difference between total linear losses and measured ohmic losses can be ascribed to the invisible ohmic losses within the catalyst layer. To elucidate this, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were taken regularly during the experiment at the current density of 100 mA cm^{-2} with the operating parameters the same like for the polarization curves. The Nyquist plots are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Nyquist plots at 100 mA cm^{-2} .

The high frequency intercept in the Nyquist plot represents the aforementioned combination of ionic resistance in the membrane together with all the electronic resistances of the cell's hardware. On the other hand, the low frequency intercept, represents total resistance of the cell, i.e. the slope of the polarization curve (dU/di), at the given current density (100 mA cm^{-2} in this case). Even though the EIS technique is far from ideal for porous electrode systems, the shape of the Nyquist plots reveals two indicative features: i) an extended $\sim 45^\circ$ slope at high frequencies, and ii) an additional small loop appearing at low frequencies. The 45° slope at high frequencies indicates distributed ohmic (mainly protonic) resistance within the CL. Due to complex, network-like, structure of CL, that consists of protonic and electronic pathways in addition to voids for the gases and product water, protonic resistance within the CL cannot be measured directly (by high frequency intercept for example). There are

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numerous papers in the literature dealing with this topic [5][6], but in general, the higher the protonic resistance within the CL, the further the 45 ° slope extends before it converts into the typical capacitance/resistance semicircle. From the Figure 11 it is visible that the high frequency slope extends slightly further with each degradation cycle, but this does not seem to be to such an extent to explain that all the unaccounted losses could be ascribed to the increased ohmic resistance within the CL:

Figure. 12 shows how the high and low frequency intercept in Nyquist diagram (from Figure 11) changed during the experiment. The increase of low frequency “resistance” shown in Figure 12 approximately corresponds to the observed increase in cell resistance from the polarization change curves (Figure 9). The cell resistance, R_{cell} , may be found by fitting the original polarization curve (at the beginning of experiment) to the equation that represents the fuel cell polarization curve, ignoring the mass transport losses, or assuming that the mass transport losses are included in R_{cell} . The value for cell resistance, R_{cell} , at the beginning of the experiment was found to be $0.165 \Omega\text{cm}^2$, and it increased almost threefold after 5000 cycles, to $0.469 \Omega\text{cm}^2$. This is also shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 Different types of resistance changes during the accelerated stress test

On the other hand, the appearance of an additional loop at low frequencies in Figure 11 indicates problems with mass transport. As it can be seen from Figure 11, at the BOL this loop is rather small, while it increases with the degradation and in the end the problems with mass transport seem to be so pronounced that it is difficult to tell the two semicircles apart. So, it is obvious that the mass transport losses have significant contribution in the overall cell losses. Still, it is quite unusual for the mass transport losses to exhibit almost linear increase

with the current density, and here they can be easily mistaken for resistive losses. The theoretical mass transport polarization curve actually behaves fairly linearly in the current region far from the limiting current, and only once the current values approach limiting current value, does the curve visibly deviate from linearity. Thus, one has to be very careful when assessing contributions of the different polarizations.

5. Conclusions

It appears that the polarization change curves may provide some insight in degradation causes into PEM fuel cells and that it is possible to differentiate between different contributions to cell degradation. This analysis may be performed on single cells as well as on the stack level. A comparison of different approaches (for ECSA assessment) and different measuring techniques (for ohmic losses) have shown that with this simple technique a pretty accurate picture of catalyst layer activity and the cell resistance can be achieved. On the other hand, distinguishing between ohmic and diffusion losses within the catalyst layer may be tricky, and even misleading. Since it is enough to quantify only one of these phenomena (the other is then simply calculated by deduction), and neither can be directly measured, further research is required to elucidate the relationship between CL degradation and the increase in the CL resistance and diffusivity.

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